

THE LEVEL OF STUDY HABITS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS OF MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

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ABSTRACT

Establishing the right study habits is a key factor in improving the student's academic performance in all areas. This study aimed to determine the level of study habits and academic performance of grade 11 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu and assess how these habits correlate to academic success. A structured survey questionnaire utilizing a 5-point Likert Scale was employed to gather the data of students. To analyze the data, the following non-parametric statistical treatments were used: the Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis to compare the study habits based on gender, strand, and age, and Spearman rho correlation to compute the relationship between study habits and academic performance. The result indicated that there are no significant differences in study habits based on age, gender, or strand. Additionally, the result also revealed that there is a weak positive relationship between the two variables: academic performance and study habits. While the majority of respondents demonstrate good study habits and achieve a "Very Satisfactory" level of academic performance, the remaining data suggests that some students still struggle with their study habits. This highlights the need to prioritize time management and active learning for students and organizations while encouraging the teachers to develop activities and provide individual support. Overall, the study revealed that good study habits play a crucial role in academic success, regardless of demographic factors.

Keywords: *Study Habits, Academic Performance, Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School*

INTRODUCTION

Education is part of every student's or adult's life. Unlike any other informal forms of socialization, education refers to the discipline that is concerned with techniques of teaching and learning in schools or school-like situations. School and education are where students can acquire knowledge of the world, develop, and foster positive relationships with people outside of their family. It is also a vehicle to land on work opportunities that people need to provide daily sustenance for their families and themselves and go on with their personal lives.

To achieve success in the field of education, study habits are utilized. Study habits are actions that include reviewing, reading, taking notes, and organizing group studies, which the students do daily to accomplish their school activities. Students develop study habits to help them learn and perform better academically. Other study habits include time management, attention, organization, and healthy habits such as having sufficient sleep before studying. Students' study habits help them retain and recall information more quickly and easily. These habits can be carried out by students throughout their academic and career journeys.

Study habits are often defined as studying without interruptions to gain necessary learning. Additionally, it shows how often a student performs in regular study activities which are identified by a regular study schedule (Sarker et al., 2024).

According to previous studies, there is a highly significant relationship between students' study habits and academic performance (Gahir et al., 2022). This means that if the students study habits are affected by various factors or improperly executed, there is a tendency that the academic performance of the students will also be affected.

According to another research, there are factors that may affect the study habits of the students negatively such as study environment, peer pressure, social media addiction, financial instability, and stress (Salcedo-Relucio, 2019). It is also stated in the research that spending less hours on studying results in poor grades. This simply means that poor time management may also affect students' productivity in studying. Hence, it is important to properly address these issues to improve one's academic experience.

Based on the researchers' initial review of the existing literature, it was found that the study concerning habits of studying and their reflection on the academic success of grade 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School were lacking. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the level of study habits of senior high school students, their academic performance, and the connection between the two variables. Another goal of this study is to figure out if study habits differ in diverse student groups. Although there are previous articles showing the results of the relationship between

educational habits and the performance of the students in school, the researchers believed that further research was needed to determine the relationship of study habits on the learners' school performance, specifically in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School Department. The findings of this study can serve as guidance for the learners in the senior high school department at Mindanao State University-Sulu in their educational journey by providing additional insights and shedding light on their study habits. Furthermore, the results can help the school faculties and administrators understand the importance and impact of study habits on their students. Overall, the study can positively contribute to the institution's ability to produce disciplined academic achievers.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of study habits of grade 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?
2. What is the level of academic performance of grade 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu?
3. Is there a significant difference in the study habits of grade 11 students in Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are grouped according to age, gender, and strand in school?
4. Is there a significant relationship of study habits to academic performance of grade 11 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study is a quantitative study that employed descriptive-correlational research design. According to McBurney & White (2009), descriptive-correlational is utilized in research studies that intend to provide static pictures of situations and at the same time form the relationship between different variables. In this study, the researchers aimed to determine the correlation of different study habits to the academic performance of the students while identifying the patterns and methods to guide the improvement of study habits among students.

Research Site

This research was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School New Building. The senior high school department is located inside the campus of MSU-Sulu, an institution established in 1974. The department offers three academic strands: GAS, STEM, and HUMSS. The senior high school building has a total of nine rooms, including the faculty room. The study was conducted among the grade 11 GAS students and grade 11 STEM students.

Research Participants

The researchers selected grade 11 students enrolled in the academic year 2024-2025 at Mindanao State University Sulu Senior High School Department, specifically from the General Academic Strand and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strands, as their respondents. In this study, the researchers used stratified random sampling, which involved the division of smaller subgroups known as strata, to balance and determine the desired sample population of the respondents.

Out of the 283 total populations of grade 11 students, the researchers selected 164 students for the sample size, 82 respondents from the three STEM sections and 82 respondents from the three GAS sections. The sample size was obtained using the Raosoft calculator. In each section, the researchers also calculated the sample size and used a spinning wheel of names to choose which student should answer the survey to ensure the objectivity of the study.

Research Instrumentation

The researchers used a survey questionnaire to collect data from each respondent. The questionnaire was a checklist survey questionnaire that utilized a 5-point Likert Scale, which included rating scales that offer options like strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. The rating scale served as a basis to determine and differentiate the respondents' degree of agreement regarding the statements about a particular category. The questionnaire used in the created by the researchers and was validated by the panels. The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section covered the demographic profile of the students such as their names, ages, genders, sections, and the general percentage average. The second part of the questionnaire contained different study habits before the written tests or examination of the students with the rating scale.

Statistical Treatment

The median was used to measure the level of study habits of the Grade 11 students, while the mean was used to measure their academic performance. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare the students' study habits based on gender and strand, while Kruskal-Wallis's test was used to compare the students' study habits according to age.

To examine the relationship between the academic performance of the students and their study habits, the Spearman rho correlation was used. The Spearman coefficient or Spearman rho correlation is like the Pearson correlation coefficient, but instead of using the actual numbers, it uses the ranking of the numbers (1st, 2nd, 3rd, etc.). It is useful for data that isn't numerical, such as ranking or categories. (Schober et al., 2018).

RESULTS

Table 1

Level of Study Habits

Item	Md	Interpretation
1. Creating a list of what to study on a specific day helps me become organized in studying.	5.00	Strongly Agree
2. Joining a study group helps me understand the lesson well.	4.00	Agree
3. I highlight important words on my notes to easily remember them.	4.00	Agree
4. I set a timer whenever I study because it helps me to stay organized.	4.00	Agree
5. I prefer studying in a quiet environment because it helps me stay focused.	5.00	Strongly Agree
6. Reviewing my lessons 2-3 weeks before the exam helps me remember it better.	4.00	Agree
7. I review the lessons after class.	4.00	Agree
8. I try to take note of everything a teacher says during class.	4.00	Agree
9. I skim on my notes to choose a specific topic to be focused.	4.00	Agree
10. Answering practice tests in advance help me prepare myself for the exam.	4.00	Agree
11. I watch videos to understand the lesson on a certain subject better.	4.00	Agree
12. I use the Feynman Technique where I read and explain the lesson to myself out loud to comprehend it more.	4.00	Agree
13. I set some goals before I study. (e.g. get a perfect or highest score in the quiz, pass the quiz, finish a topic before the day ends, etc.)	4.00	Agree
14. I prefer listening to music while studying.	3.00	Undecided
15. I change my scenery to improve my memory and concentration.	4.00	Agree

Legend: 1.00 = Strongly Disagree, 2.00 = Disagree, 3.00 = Undecided, 4.00 = Agree, 5.00 = Strongly Agree

Table 2

Level of Academic Performance

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Academic Performance	88.77%	3.47	Very Satisfactory

Legend: Outstanding = 90-100, Very Satisfactory = 85-89, Satisfactory = 80-84, Fairly Satisfactory = 75-79, Did Not Meet Expectations = Below 75

Table 3.1

Significant Difference of Study Habits of students when the data are grouped according to age

Study Habits	15-16 years old		17-18 years old		19 years old and above		x ² (3)	df	p-value
	N	Mean Rank	N	Mean Rank	N	Mean Rank			
	124	85.56	33	71.00	7	82.57	2.456	2	.293

Table 3.2

Significant Difference of Study Habits of students when the data are grouped according to gender

Study Habits	Male		Female		U	W	Z	p-value
	N	Mean Rank	N	Mean Rank				
	62	74.04	102	87.64	2637.50	4590.50	-1.781	.075

*Significant at $p > 0.05$

Table 3.3

Significant Difference of Study Habits of students when the data are grouped according to strand

Study Habits	STEM	GAS	U	W	Z	p-value
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N	Mean Rank	N	Mean Rank				
82	84.84	82	80.16	3170.50	6573.50	-.631	.528

Table 4

Relationship between Study Habits and Academic Performance of Students

Variable	n	1	2
Academic Performance	164	-	
Level of Study Habits	164	.207**	-

DISCUSSION

Table 1 results show the level of study habits of students using Median. Results show that the median scores for most study habit indicators ranged from 4.00 (Agree) to 5.00 (Strongly Agree), suggesting that students generally exhibited good study habits. Notably, SH1 and SH5 had the highest ratings, indicating strong adherence to effective routines. However, SH14 had the lowest median (3.00, Undecided), suggesting that some students struggled with certain study habits.

In relation to this finding, Labrador et al. (2024) found out that students exhibit good study habits, particularly in areas such as time management, examination preparation, reading comprehension, note-taking, and memory retention. Their findings highlight that students actively apply strategies to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of their learning processes. Academic achievement displays through such behaviors illustrates how students deliver performance effectively thanks to their well-developed study habits.

Table 2 results show the level of academic performance of students using Mean. Result shows that the General Percentage Average (GPA) of the 164 students ranges from 74.64% to 96.25%, with a mean GPA of 88.77% and a standard deviation of 3.48. Based on the Department of Education's grading scale, this average falls within the "Very Satisfactory" range (85–89%). This suggests that, on average, the students generally perform at a high academic level.

Similar to what Castro et. al. (2023) revealed in their study, 44% or 80 of their respondents, who are all Grade 12 students, showcased a very satisfactory level of academic performance which is within the grade scale 85-89 (Very Satisfactory).

On Table 3.3, the result of the significant difference of study habits of students when the data are grouped according to strand was obtained using the Mann-Whitney U test. Based on the table above, there is no significant difference in the study habits

between STEM students (mean rank = 84.84) and GAS students (mean rank = 80.16); $U = 3170.50$, $W = 6573.50$, $Z = -.631$, $p = > .075$. This can be concluded that the study habits of Grade 11 STEM and GAS students do not significantly differ.

The Spearman's rho correlation was used to assess the relationship between the study habits and academic performance of Grade 11 students. According to the results in table 4, the two variables have a weakly positive correlation with [$r = 0.207$ ($p = 0.008$)]. This means that when one variable increases, the other variable tends to increase as well. This suggests that as the students' study habits improve, their academic performance also improves, and vice versa.

Many relative studies suggest the same outcomes. A study by Princy et al. (2023) concludes a strong positive correlation between study habits and academic performance with nursing students as their respondents. This suggests that students with acquired study habits happen to achieve higher academic success than those with poor study habits. It highlights the strong link between study habits and academic success, emphasizing the need for student engagement, faculty support, and improved learning skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that study habits played a crucial role in the academic performance of Grade 11 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Good study habits enable the students to perform well and be engaged in different classroom settings and subjects. It promotes discipline and responsible studentship. Based on the findings, it can also be concluded that most students exhibited good study habits, which aligned with their relatively high academic performance. The correlation analysis confirmed a positive relationship between study habits and academic performance, indicating that students who developed effective study habits tended to achieve better academic results.

Additionally, the study revealed that factors such as age, gender, and academic strand did not significantly influence study habits or academic performance. This suggested that regardless of demographic differences, cultivating strong study habits remained a key factor in academic success.

Overall, this study highlighted the importance of reinforcing effective study habits among students to enhance their academic performance

Recommendations

They should continue prioritizing time management, active learning, and seeking help from teachers, friends, or advisors when needed. They should develop more good study habits to continue achieving a very satisfactory performance in school or even improve until they reach the level of excellence. The school administrators should start creating a school environment that supports learning and good study habits. They should

also provide resources like workshops, tutoring, and more study spaces to help students improve their study skills. The Future Researchers should look deeper into how study skills affect academic performance. They should also identify the most effective study habits to improve student achievement. Moreover, they should conduct a study that is not limited to STEM and GAS students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The aim of the research ethics protocol in this study is to ensure that no one is harmed during any research activities. Therefore, appropriate precautions were incorporated into this study based on ethical standards and considerations. Researchers safeguarded the welfare, rights, privacy, and dignity of research participants by adhering by ethical standards. The researchers handled the information obtained for this study with confidentiality and was used solely for academic purposes. Additionally, the names of the respondents were not mentioned in this study.

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